

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of novel *N*-maltosylated thiocarbamides, benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides and thiocarbamates

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Abstract : A new class of *N*-maltosides has been investigated in which maltosyl isothiocyanate was readily transformed into corresponding 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides, 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-3-substituted benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides and 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-*O*-alkyl thiocarbamates on reaction with aryl amines, 2-aminobenzothiazoles/substituted benzothiazoles and alcohols. These compound were screened for their antimicrobial activity against *P. vulgaris*, *E. coli*, *S. typhimurium*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *A. niger*, *Mucor* and *Riazoctomia*.

Keywords : Maltosyl bromide, maltosyl isothiocyanate, thiocarbamides, benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides, thiocarbamates, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Recently, we have reported the synthesis of certain *N*- and *S*-glycosides^{1,2} and studied their biological activities. Besides that a large number of the nitrosoureas bearing a maltosyl group have been reported to exhibit strong anti-tumor activities against Leukemia L 1210 or Ehrlich ascites carcinoma³. Therefore, in the present note we report the synthesis of a series of *N*-maltosylated thiocarbamides, benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides and thiocarbamates and their antimicrobial activities.

Synthesis of the 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides (**4a-g**), 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-3-substituted benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides (**6a-g**) and 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-*O*-alkyl thiocarbamates (**8a-e**) were performed by the interaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl isothiocyanate (**2**) with various aryl amines (**3a-g**), substituted benzothiazoles (**5a-g**) and alcohols (**7a-e**) (Scheme 1).

Antimicrobial activity :

Antibacterial activity : All the compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity against various bacteria such as *P. vulgaris*, *E. coli*, *S. typhimurium*, *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* by cup plate method at concentration 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in DMSO by using the standard cotrimazine (25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) for bacteria. Some of the tested

compounds exhibited moderate and strongest inhibitory activity against the tested strains of bacteria.

Antifungal activity : All the compounds were screened for their antifungal activities by using cup plate method at concentration 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in DMSO by using the standard griseofulvin (10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) against various fungus such as *A. niger*, *Mucor* and *Riazoctomia*. Some of these tested compounds exhibited moderate and strongest inhibitory activity against the tested strains of fungus.

Experimental

General procedure :

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in Nujol, KBr on a FT-IR Perkin-Elmer RXI (4000–450 cm^{-1}) spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR measurements were performed on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) NMR spectrometer in CDCl₃ solution with TMS as internal reference. The mass spectra FAB were recorded on a JEOL SX-102 Mass spectrometer. Optical rotations [α]_D³¹ were measured on a Equip-Tronics Digital Polarimeter EQ-800 at 31 °C in CHCl₃. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on silica gel G for TLC (Merck) and spots were visualized by iodine vapour/UV chamber. Kjeldahl's method was used for nitrogen estimation.

Maltosyl bromide

1-Hepta-O-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl isothiocyanate

Scheme 1

where, Bz = COC_6H_5

4a : R = Phenyl; 4b : R = *o*-Cl-phenyl; 4c : R = *m*-Cl-phenyl; 4d : R = *p*-Cl-phenyl; 4e : R = *o*-tolyl;

4f : R = *m*-tolyl; 4g : R = *p*-tolyl

Scheme 2

6a : R = H; 6b : R = 4-Cl; 6c : R = 5-Cl; 6d : R = 6-Cl; 6e : 4-Me; 6f : R = 5-Me; 6g : R = 6-Me

Scheme 3

8a : R = Methyl; 8b : R = Ethyl; 8c : R = *n*-Propyl; 8d : R = Isopropyl; 8e : R = Tertiary butyl

Scheme 4

Synthesis of 1-hepta-O-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl isothiocyanate (2) :

A reaction mixture of 1-hepta-O-benzoyl- α -D-maltosyl

bromide (1) (15 g, 0.01 mmol) and lead thiocyanate (4.2 g, 0.01 mmol) in anhydrous xylene (150 mL) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC.

After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was brought to a room temperature and filtered. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the sticky mass obtained as residue was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C). A granular pale yellow solid was obtained (Scheme 1). This was purified by chloroform-ether and recrystallized from ethanol-water.

2 : Yield : 13 g (88.31%); m.p. 145 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{31} = +29.60^\circ$ (c , 1.013 in CHCl_3); R_f 0.80 (petroleum ether : EtOAc, 1 : 1); IR (KBr) : 2027 (N=C=S), 1726 (C=O), 1272 (C–O), 1096–1028 and 936 cm^{-1} (characteristic of maltose); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 8.08–7.9 (35H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$), 5.9–3.9 (14H, m, maltose ring protons); FABMS (m/z) : 1111 (M^+), 1053 ($\text{HBM}^+ = \text{M-NCS}$), 1034 ($\text{M-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 1006 ($\text{M-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 990 ($\text{M-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 976 ($\text{M-C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$), 948 ($\text{HBM-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 932 ($\text{HBM-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 918 ($\text{HBM-C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$), 827 ($\text{HBM-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$, $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 579 ($\text{TBG}^+ = \text{HBM-C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8$), 474 ($\text{TBG-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 353 ($\text{TBG-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 135 ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2^+$), 105 ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}^+$), 77 (C_6H_5^+) (Found : C, 66.96; H, 4.45; N, 1.10; S, 3.11. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{62}\text{H}_{49}\text{O}_{17}\text{NS}$: C, 66.98; H, 4.41; N, 1.26; S, 2.88%).

Synthesis of 1-hepta-O-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-3-phenyl thiocarbamides (4a) :

Aniline **3a** (0.29 g, 0.003 mmol) was added to a benzene solution of 1-hepta-O-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl isothiocyanate (**2**) (3.5 g in 25 mL of benzene). This reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC. Then it was brought to room temperature and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the sticky mass obtained as residue was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C). A granular pale yellow solid (3.5 g, 92.34%) was obtained (**4a-g**). It was purified by recrystallization from ethanol-water, m.p. 142–146 °C. The physical characterization results are summarized in Table 1 (**4a-g**). Compounds **4b-g** were also prepared by similar method.

4a : IR (KBr) : 3356 (N–H), 3065 (Ar–H), 2958 (aliph. C–H), 1725 (C=O), 1532 (C=N), 1316 (C–N), 1270 (C–O), 1096–1028 and 936 cm^{-1} (characteristic of maltose); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 8.09–7.03 (40H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$ and Ar–H), 6.77–6.74 (1H, d, N–H), 6.17 (1H, s, N–H), 5.89–4.40 (14H, m, maltose ring protons); FABMS (m/z) : 1204 (M^+), 1083 ($\text{M-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 1053 ($\text{M-C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{S}$),

976 ($\text{HBM-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 948 ($\text{HBM-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 932 ($\text{HBM-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 918 ($\text{HBM-C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$), 579 ($\text{TBG}^+ = \text{HBM-C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8$), 135 ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2^+$), 105 ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}^+$), 77 (C_6H_5) (Found : C, 67.70; H, 4.70; N, 2.12; S, 2.74. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{68}\text{H}_{49}\text{O}_{17}\text{NS}$: C, 67.77; H, 4.65; N, 2.32; S, 2.26%).

4b : IR (KBr) : 3405 (N–H), 3069 (Ar–H), 2955 (aliph. C–H), 1724 (C=O), 1539 (C=N), 1316 (C–N), 1272 (C–O), 1098–1028 and 936 cm^{-1} (characteristic of maltose); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 8.05–7.19 (39H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$ and Ar–H), 6.77–6.74 (1H, d, N–H), 6.17–6.14 (1H, s, N–H), 5.90–4.0 (14H, m, maltose ring protons); FABMS (m/z) : 1238 (M^+), 1203 (M-Cl), 1133 ($\text{M-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 1117 ($\text{M-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 1103 ($\text{M-C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$), 1053 ($\text{HBM}^+ = \text{M-C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$), 976 ($\text{HBM-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 948 ($\text{HBM-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 932 ($\text{HBM-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 918 ($\text{HBM-C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$), 579 ($\text{TBG}^+ = \text{HBM-C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8$), 135 ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2^+$), 105 ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}^+$), 77 (C_6H_5) (Found : C, 65.97; H, 4.47; N, 2.24; S, 2.89. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{68}\text{H}_{55}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$: C, 65.91; H, 4.41; N, 2.26; S, 2.58%).

4c : IR (KBr) : 3345 (N–H), 3067 (Ar–H), 2959 (aliph. C–H), 1729 (C=O), 1527 (C=N), 1316 (C–N), 1270 (C–O), 1096–1027 and 936 cm^{-1} (characteristic of maltose); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 8.31–7.19 (39H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$ and Ar–H), 6.75–6.72 (1H, d, N–H), 6.10 (1H, s, N–H), 5.79–4.26 (14H, m, maltose ring protons); FABMS (m/z) : 1238 (M^+), 1203 (M-Cl), 1133 ($\text{M-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 1117 ($\text{M-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 1103 ($\text{M-C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$), 1053 ($\text{HBM}^+ = \text{M-C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$), 976 ($\text{HBM-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 948 ($\text{HBM-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 932 ($\text{HBM-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 918 ($\text{HBM-C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$), 579 ($\text{TBG}^+ = \text{HBM-C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8$), 135 ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2^+$), 105 ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}^+$), 77 (C_6H_5^+) (Found : C, 65.95; H, 4.45; N, 2.12; S, 2.74. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{68}\text{H}_{55}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$: C, 65.91; H, 4.41; N, 2.26; S, 2.58%).

4d : IR (KBr) : 3425 (N–H), 3069 (Ar–H), 2957 (aliph. C–H), 1725 (C=O), 1527 (C=N), 1316 (C–N), 1272.1 (C–O), 1095–1027 and 936 cm^{-1} (characteristic of maltose); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 8.02–7.25 (39H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$ and Ar–H), 6.99–6.97 (1H, d, N–H), 6.86–6.83 (1H, s, N–H), 6.17–3.89 (14H, m, maltose ring protons); FABMS (m/z) : 1238 (M^+), 1203 (M-Cl), 1133 ($\text{M-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 1117 ($\text{M-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 1103 ($\text{M-C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$), 1053 ($\text{HBM}^+ = \text{M-C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$), 976 ($\text{HBM-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 948 ($\text{HBM-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 932 ($\text{HBM-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 918 ($\text{HBM-C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$), 579 ($\text{TBG}^+ = \text{HBM-C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8$), 135 ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2^+$), 105 ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}^+$), 77

Table 1. Physical data characterization of compounds 4a-g, 6a-g and 8a-e

Reactant	g	Product	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	R _f value	[α] ³¹ _D CHCl ₃
Aniline	0.29	4a	92.34	142–146	0.71	+29.80 (1.006)
<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	0.40	4b	79.99	149–151	0.75	+69.06 (0.986)
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	0.40	4c	98.32	140	0.62	-50.33 (0.993)
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	0.40	4d	91.88	155(d)	0.54	-39.73 (1.006)
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	0.33	4e	83.62	145–149	0.66	-60 (1.00)
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	0.33	4f	91.21	132(d)	0.80	-40 (1.00)
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	0.33	4g	90.99	142–148	0.59	+19.86 (1.006)
2-Amino benzothiazole	0.47	6a	97.28	132–134	0.75	+67.20 (1.00)
2-Amino (4-Cl) benzothiazole	0.57	6b	95.17	136–138	0.81	+90.93 (1.00)
2-Amino (5-Cl) benzothiazole	0.57	6c	96.61	126–128	0.77	+77.75 (1.00)
2-Amino (6-Cl) benzothiazole	0.57	6d	95.17	150–152	0.69	+112 (1.00)
2-Amino (4-Me) benzothiazole	0.51	6e	98.66	124–126	0.54	+94.88 (1.00)
2-Amino (5-Me) benzothiazole	0.51	6f	95.78	140–142	0.59	+71.60 (1.00)
2-Amino (6-Me) benzothiazole	0.51	6g	94.22	128–130	0.83	+54.90 (1.00)
Methanol	30	8a	80.55	137–140	0.85	+40 (1.00)
Ethanol	30	8b	68.68	120–123	0.80	+90.13 (0.946)
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	30	8c	81.52	132–135	0.70	+162.2 (0.986)
Isopropyl alcohol	30	8d	84.23	128–130	0.78	+110 (1.00)
Tertiary butyl alcohol	30	8e	91.15	185(d)	0.76	+60 (1.00)

Satisfactory C and H analyses found in all cases.

(C₆H₅⁺) (Found : C, 65.95; H, 4.45; N, 2.12; S, 2.74. Calcd. for C₆₈H₅₅O₁₇N₂SCl : C, 65.91; H, 4.41; N, 2.26; S, 2.58%).

4e : IR (KBr) : 3444 (N-H), 3066 (Ar-H), 2956 (aliph. C-H), 1725 (C=O), 1530 (C=N), 1316 (C-N), 1271 (C-O), 1096–1027 and 936 cm⁻¹ (characteristic of maltose); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 8.07–7.0 (39H, m, 7COC₆H₅ and Ar-H), 6.71–6.66 (1H, d, N-H) and 6.45–6.42 (1H, s, N-H), 5.87–3.89 (14H, m, maltose ring protons), 2.16 (3H, s, -CH₃); FABMS (*m/z*) : 1218 (M⁺), 1113 (M-C₇H₅O), 1097 (M-C₇H₅O₂), 1053 (HBM⁺=M-C₈H₉N₂S), 976 (HBM-C₆H₅), 948 (HBM-C₇H₅O), 932 (HBM-C₇H₅O₂), 918 (HBM-C₈H₇O₂), 579 (TBG⁺=HBM-C₂₇H₂₂O₈), 135 (C₈H₇O₂⁺), 105 (C₇H₅O⁺), 77 (C₆H₅⁺)

(Found : C, 68.01; H, 4.78; N, 2.14; S, 2.87. Calcd. for C₆₉H₅₈O₁₇N₂S : C, 67.98; H, 4.76; N, 2.29; S, 2.62%).

4f : IR (KBr) : 3449 (N-H), 3066 (Ar-H), 2958 (aliph. C-H), 1727 (C=O), 1541 (C=N), 1316 (C-N), 1271 (C-O), 1096–1028 and 936 cm⁻¹ (characteristic of maltose); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.99–7.25 (39H, m, 7COC₆H₅ and Ar-H), 6.84 (1H, d, N-H), 6.75 (1H, s, N-H), 6.10–4.42 (14H, m, maltose ring protons), 2.29 (3H, s, -CH₃); FABMS (*m/z*) : 1218 (M⁺), 1113 (M-C₇H₅O), 1097 (M-C₇H₅O₂), 1053 (HBM⁺=M-C₈H₉N₂S), 976 (HBM-C₆H₅), 948 (HBM-C₇H₅O), 932 (HBM-C₇H₅O₂), 918 (HBM-C₈H₇O₂), 579 (TBG⁺=HBM-C₂₇H₂₂O₈), 135 (C₈H₇O₂⁺), 105 (C₇H₅O⁺), 77 (C₆H₅⁺) (Found : C,

68.07; H, 4.49; N, 2.26; S, 2.87. Calcd. for $C_{69}H_{58}O_{17}N_2S$: C, 67.98; H, 4.76; N, 2.29; S, 2.62%.

4g: IR (KBr): 3383 (N-H), 3065 (Ar-H), 2961 (aliph. C-H), 1725 (C=O), 1532 (C=N), 1316 (C-N), 1271 (C-O), 1097–1028 and 936 cm^{-1} (characteristic of maltose); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 8.06–7.13 (39H, m, 7 COC_6H_5 and Ar-H), 6.91–6.88 (1H, d, N-H), 6.72–6.70 (1H, s, N-H), 5.90–4.42 (14H, m, maltose ring protons), 2.35 (3H, s, $-CH_3$); FABMS (m/z): 1218 (M^+), 1113 (M- C_7H_5O), 1097 (M- $C_7H_5O_2$), 1053 (HBM $^+$ =M- $C_8H_9N_2S$), 976 (HBM- C_6H_5), 948 (HBM- C_7H_5O), 932 (HBM- $C_7H_5O_2$), 918 (HBM- $C_8H_7O_2$), 579 (TBG $^+$ =HBM- $C_{27}H_{22}O_8$), 135 ($C_8H_7O_2^+$), 105 ($C_7H_5O^+$), 77 ($C_6H_5^+$) (Found: C, 68.20; H, 4.47; N, 2.20; S, 2.97. Calcd. for $C_{69}H_{58}O_{17}N_2S$: C, 67.98; H, 4.76; N, 2.29; S, 2.62%).

Synthesis of 1-hepta-O-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-3-(2)-benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides (6a):

A solution of 2-aminobenzothiazole **5a** (0.47 g, 0.003 mmol in 20 mL of benzene) was added to hepta-O-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl isothiocyanate (**2**) (3.5 g, 0.003 mmol in 40 mL of benzene). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was brought to room temperature and the solvent removed under vacuum to give sticky residue which was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to give a pale yellow solid (3.8 g, 97.28%). This was purified by recrystallization from ethanol-water, m.p. 132–134 °C. The physical characterization results are summarized in Table 1 (**6a-g**). Compound **6b-g** were synthesized by similar method.

6a: IR (KBr): 3439 (N-H), 3066 (Ar-H), 2958 (aliph. C-H), 1728 (C=O), 1534 (C=N), 1315 (C-N), 1270 (C-O), 1095–1027 and 936 cm^{-1} (characteristic of maltose); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 8.09–7.22 (39H, m, 7 COC_6H_5 and Ar-H), 6.78–6.72 (1H, d, N-H), 6.10–6.07 (1H, s, N-H), 5.79–4.30 (14H, m, maltose ring protons); FABMS (m/z): 1261 (M^+), 1156 (M- C_7H_5O), 1140 (M- $C_7H_5O_2$), 1126 (M- $C_8H_7O_2$), 1053 (HBM $^+$ =M- $C_8H_6N_3S_2$), 976 (HBM- C_6H_5), 948 (HBM- C_7H_5O), 932 (HBM- $C_7H_5O_2$), 918 (HBM- $C_8H_7O_2$), 579 (TBG $^+$ =HBM- $C_{27}H_{22}O_8$), 135 ($C_8H_7O_2^+$), 105 ($C_7H_5O^+$), 77 ($C_6H_5^+$) (Found: C, 69.57; H, 4.66; N, 3.23; S, 5.33. Calcd. for $C_{69}H_{55}O_{17}N_3S_2$: C, 68.04; H, 4.36; N, 3.33; S, 5.07%).

6b: IR (KBr): 3449 (N-H), 3066 (Ar-H), 2958 (aliph. C-H), 1728 (C=O), 1530 (C=N), 1316 (C-N), 1270 (C=O), 1096–1026 and 936 cm^{-1} (characteristic of maltose); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 7.99–7.23 (38H, m, 7 COC_6H_5 and Ar-H), 6.76–6.75 (1H, d, N-H), 6.66–6.60 (1H, s, N-H), 6.16–4.42 (14H, m, maltose ring protons); FABMS (m/z): 1295 (M^+), 1260 (M-Cl), 1190 (M- C_7H_5O), 1174 (M- $C_7H_5O_2$), 1160 (M- $C_8H_7O_2$), 1053 (HBM $^+$ =M- $C_8H_5N_3S_2Cl$), 976 (HBM- C_6H_5), 948 (HBM- C_7H_5O), 932 (HBM- $C_7H_5O_2$), 918 (HBM- $C_8H_7O_2$), 579 (TBG $^+$ =HBM- $C_{27}H_{22}O_8$), 474 (TBG- C_7H_5O), 444 (TBG- $C_8H_7O_2$), 135 ($C_8H_7O_2^+$), 105 ($C_7H_5O^+$), 77 ($C_6H_5^+$) (Found: C, 64.01; H, 4.27; N, 3.10; S, 5.31. Calcd. for $C_{69}H_{54}O_{17}N_3S_2Cl$: C, 63.93; H, 4.16; N, 3.24; S, 4.94%).

6c: 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 8.68–7.20 (38H, m, 7 COC_6H_5 and Ar-H), 6.76–6.75 (1H, d, N-H), 6.67–6.64 (1H, s, N-H), 6.13–4.29 (14H, m, maltose ring protons) (Found: C, 64.55; H, 4.32; N, 3.07; S, 5.12. Calcd. for $C_{69}H_{54}O_{17}N_3S_2Cl$: C, 63.93; H, 4.16; N, 3.24; S, 4.94%).

6d: 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 8.13–7.28 (38H, m, 7 COC_6H_5 and Ar-H), 6.96 (1H, d, N-H), 6.78–6.77 (1H, s, N-H), 6.08–3.98 (14H, m, maltose ring protons) (Found: C, 64.76; H, 4.23; N, 3.12; S, 5.34. Calcd. for $C_{69}H_{54}O_{17}N_3S_2Cl$: C, 63.93; H, 4.16; N, 3.24; S, 4.94%).

6e: 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 8.60–7.20 (38H, m, 7 COC_6H_5 and Ar-H), 6.76–6.75 (1H, d, N-H), 6.66–6.64 (1H, s, N-H), 6.13–4.29 (14H, m, maltose ring protons), 2.56–2.50 (3H, s, $-CH_3$) (Found: C, 66.54; H, 4.87; N, 3.21; S, 5.26. Calcd. for $C_{70}H_{57}O_{17}N_3S_2$: C, 65.88; H, 4.47; N, 3.29; S, 5.01%).

6f: 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 8.55–7.20 (38H, m, 7 COC_6H_5 and Ar-H), 6.76–6.75 (1H, d, N-H), 6.68–6.64 (1H, s, N-H), 6.13–4.29 (14H, m, maltose ring protons), 2.48 (3H, s, $-CH_3$) (Found: C, 65.90; H, 4.89; N, 3.23; S, 5.37. Calcd. for $C_{70}H_{57}O_{17}N_3S_2$: C, 65.88; H, 4.47; N, 3.29; S, 5.01%).

6g: IR (KBr): 3449 (N-H), 3067 (Ar-H), 2960 (aliph. C-H), 1728 (C=O), 1530 (C=N), 1316 (C-N), 1270 (C-O), 1097–1026 and 936 cm^{-1} (characteristic of maltose); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 8.09–7.22 (38H, m, 7 COC_6H_5 and Ar-H), 6.76–6.75 (1H, d, N-H), 6.66 (1H, s, N-H),

6.10–4.30 (14H, m, maltose ring protons), 2.35 (3H, s, -CH₃); FABMS (*m/z*): 1275 (M⁺), 1260 (M-CH₃), 1198 (M-C₆H₅), 1170 (M-C₇H₅O), 1154 (M-C₇H₅O₂), 1140 (M-C₈H₇O₂), 1093 (M-C₆H₅, C₇H₅O), 1053 (HBM⁺ = M-C₉H₈N₃S₂), 976 (HBM-C₆H₅), 948 (HBM-C₇H₅O), 932 (HBM-C₇H₅O₂), 918 (HBM-C₈H₇O₂), 579 (TBG⁺ = HBM-C₂₇H₂₂O₈), 474 (TBG-C₇H₅O), 458 (TBG-C₇H₅O₂), 353 (TBG-C₇H₅O, C₇H₅O₂), 135 (C₈H₇O₂⁺), 105 (C₇H₅O⁺), 77 (C₆H₅⁺) (Found: C, 67.20; H, 4.51; N, 3.18; S, 5.11. Calcd. for C₇₀H₅₇O₁₇N₃S₂: C, 65.88; H, 4.47; N, 3.29; S, 5.01%).

Synthesis of 1-hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-maltosyl-O-methyl thiocarbamates (8a) :

A solution of 1-hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-maltosyl isothiocyanate (**2**) (3.5 g, 0.003 mmol) in dry methanol **7a** (30 mL) was refluxed for 3 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC) the reaction mixture was allowed to reach to room temperature and then it was poured on ice water with constant stirring. The white solid thus formed was filtered and dried (2.9 g, 80.55%). m.p. 137–140 °C. The physical characterization results are summarized in Table 1 (**8a-g**). Compound **8b-e** were synthesized by similar method.

8a : (Found: C, 67; H, 4.44; N, 1.03; S, 2.98. Calcd. for C₆₃H₅₃O₁₈NS: C, 66.14; H, 4.63; N, 1.22; S, 2.79%).

8b : IR (KBr) : 3449 (N-H), 3067 (Ar-H), 2962 (aliph. C-H), 1728 (C=O), 1316 (C-N), 1271 (C-O), 1096–1028 and 937 cm⁻¹ (characteristic of maltose); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 8.25–7.26 (35H, m, 7COC₆H₅), 6.98 (1H, d, N-H), 5.73–3.94 (14H, m, maltose ring protons), 3.0 (2H, q, -CH₂), 1.25–1.20 (3H, t, -CH₃); FABMS (*m/z*) : 1157 (M⁺), 1080 (M-C₆H₅), 1036 (M-C₇H₅O₂), 1022 (M-C₈H₇O₂), 1053 (HBM⁺ = M-C₃H₆NSO), 976 (HBM-C₆H₅), 948 (HBM-C₇H₅O), 932 (HBM-C₇H₅O₂), 579 (TBG⁺ = HBM-C₂₇H₂₂O₈), 135 (C₈H₇O₂⁺), 105 (C₇H₅O⁺), 77 (C₆H₅⁺) (Found: C, 65.20; H, 4.30; N, 1.19; S, 2.80. Calcd. for C₆₄H₅₅O₁₈NS: C, 66.37; H, 4.75; N, 1.21; S, 2.76%).

8c : IR (KBr) : 3448 (N-H), 3068 (Ar-H), 2964 (aliph. C-H), 1730 (C=O), 1316 (C-N), 1270 (C-O), 1096–1029 and 937 cm⁻¹ (characteristic of maltose); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 8.3.4–7.20 (35H, m, 7COC₆H₅), 6.98 (1H, d, N-H), 5.73–4.25 (14H, m, maltose ring protons), 3.88

(2H, sextet, -CH₂), 3.48 (2H, t, -CH₂), 1.89–1.87 (3H, t, -CH₃); FABMS (*m/z*) : 1171 (M⁺), 1094 (M-C₆H₅), 1066 (M-C₇H₅O), 1050 (M-C₇H₅O₂), 1036 (M-C₈H₇O₂), 1053 (HBM⁺ = M-C₄H₈NSO), 976 (HBM-C₆H₅), 948 (HBM-C₇H₅O), 932 (HBM-C₇H₅O₂), 579 (TBG⁺ = HBM-C₂₇H₂₂O₈), 474 (TBG-C₇H₅O), 458 (TBG-C₇H₅O₂), 353 (TBG-C₇H₅O, C₇H₅O₂), 135 (C₈H₇O₂⁺), 105 (C₇H₅O⁺), 77 (C₆H₅⁺) (Found: C, 66.77; H, 4.77; N, 1.10; S, 2.91. Calcd. for C₆₅H₅₇O₁₈NS: C, 66.60; H, 4.86; N, 1.19; S, 2.73%).

8d : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 8.34–7.2 (35H, m, 7COC₆H₅), 6.98 (1H, d, N-H), 5.74–4.25 (14H, m, maltose ring protons), 3.95–3.93 (1H, septet, -CH), 1.88–1.86 (6H, d, -2CH₃); FABMS (*m/z*) : 1171 (M⁺), 1172 (M⁺+1), 1112 (M-C₃H₇), 1094 (M-C₆H₅), 1066 (M-C₇H₅O), 1050 (M-C₇H₅O₂), 1036 (M-C₈H₇O₂), 1053 (HBM⁺ = M-C₄H₈NSO), 976 (HBM-C₆H₅), 948 (HBM-C₇H₅O), 932 (HBM-C₇H₅O₂), 918 (HBM-C₈H₇O₂), 579 (TBG⁺ = HBM-C₂₇H₂₂O₈), 474 (TBG-C₇H₅O), 458 (TBG-C₇H₅O₂), 353 (TBG-C₇H₅O, C₇H₅O₂), 135 (C₈H₇O₂⁺), 105 (C₇H₅O⁺), 77 (C₆H₅⁺) (Found: C, 66.89; H, 4.69; N, 1.11; S, 2.97. Calcd. for C₆₅H₅₇O₁₈NS: C, 66.60; H, 4.86; N, 1.19; S, 2.73%).

8e : (Found: C, 67.15; H, 4.74; N, 1.15; S, 2.89. Calcd. for C₆₆H₅₉O₁₈NS: C, 66.83; H, 4.97; N, 1.18; S, 2.70%).

HBM⁺ = Hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-maltosyl, TBG⁺ = Tetra-O-benzoyl-β-glucosyl.

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